

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Agile Datum

9 – 13 December 2019

Automating the evaluation
of local government planning
applications

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1 Executive summary

1.1 Context

It is estimated that England requires up to 345,000 new homes to be built each year in order to keep up with population growth [1]. Although housebuilding has increased since reaching a low point after the financial crisis, the annual net supply of new homes would need to increase by more than 40% to reach this number [1]. This lack of new homes contributes to higher mortgages, higher rents, less social housing and wider deprivation.

One of the contributing factors is that the current planning application system remains a complex and inefficient task. Every construction project in the UK, including building or extending a house, fitting new windows on a listed building, or chopping down a tree, requires the submission of complicated planning forms and technical drawings. Each one of these documents needs to be manually validated and approved by a planning officer.

Over 3.5 million applications are submitted to councils each year. On average, owing to local government budget cuts of 40% over the last 10 years, it takes three weeks for a council to start looking at a planning application. This creates large backlogs and a lack of information for application submitters, leading to additional calls and emails to chase progress which further increase workload on planning officers. At the same time, over a third (1.2 million) of the applications submitted annually are rejected, often owing to the complexity of submitting a correct application and the manual burden in processing them at councils.

1.2 Challenge Overview

It takes a planning officer 30-60 minutes to validate whether the information in planning forms and drawings is correct. This manual validation represents around 250,000 person hours of administration per year. Independent research conducted by Agile Datum shows that over 80% of planning application rejections occur due to 12 common mistakes. These errors can be categorised into issues in application forms and in planning drawings, as follows:

Common Errors in Form Submissions:

- Incorrect application form used.
- Incorrect application fee calculated.
- Incomplete sections in the form.
- The description of the work does not match the drawings.
- Missing supporting documents.

- Incorrect units, such as for the crowns of trees.

Common Errors in Planning Drawing Submissions:

- Missing or incorrect floor plans.
- Missing or incorrect elevations.
- Missing or incorrect scales.
- Missing true north arrow.
- Missing or incorrect block/site plans.
- Planning drawings do not match the planning form descriptions.

Agile Datum aims to use artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) to detect and classify planning drawings and application forms, in order to automatically detect the 12 common mistakes above. This would greatly reduce the amount of time it takes a planning officer to validate and approve a planning application, thus leading to a faster, more streamlined planning process. Applicants could also be immediately informed of any issues and take action to correct them before the application is reviewed.

This is a complex challenge due to there being no standardised format for the applications. Different forms with different fields are used (even within a single council) and there are no standard templates for drawing submission. The plans and forms are all submitted in PDFs in various layouts, formats and contents. As a result, a planning drawing may have multiple items (floor plans, elevations or side perspectives, site maps, scales etc.) and it could have multiple copies (e.g. existing floor plans and proposed floor plans). For example, there could be three sets of drawings with three associated sets of scales marked. Hence, the ability to detect the type of an object (such as a scale) and link it to the relevant elements in an application (such as a floor plan) is essential.

1.3 Data overview

For this challenge a dataset consisting of the 1787 planning applications that were active in the London Borough of Redbridge between 1 January 2019 and 30 September 2019 is used. All files for individual applications are publicly available from the Redbridge planning portal [2], but Agile Datum has access to this combined dataset via agreement with Redbridge. Private information such as contact details are redacted in all the files.

Each application typically contains around ten supporting documents, each in PDF format, meaning the full dataset comprises of over 17,000 files (and each file may contain several pages). These include application forms, planning drawings (floor plans, site plans and elevations) and sometimes other correspondence, photographs or reports. Even though the dataset covers only one council there is no standard layout for the documents (as previously mentioned).

The data is described in detail in Section 2.

1.4 Main objectives

The overall objective of this work is to move towards the automated detection of common errors in planning applications using ML/AI approaches. After reviewing the common errors and the dataset we set the following objectives, which can be viewed as critical first steps:

1. **Conversion of PDFs into model-suitable formats:** PDFs cannot typically be directly input to a model, and the files come in many different types without a standard format. This makes the dataset challenging from a data science perspective. A pipeline is needed to convert PDFs into text, images and other formats that can be ingested by a model.
2. **Categorise the type and contents of planning application documents:** Many of the common errors relate to required information not being supplied, for example whether existing and proposed drawings have been provided or whether all sections of a form have been completed. To be able to determine whether this is the case, it's necessary to categorise files (which may have meaningless names, for example) and their contents (proposed and existing drawings may be within the same file, for example).

The above objectives do not consider common errors relating to whether the supplied information is *correct*, which was out of scope of this challenge given the time constraints. However, the output of the two objectives above are required to answer these questions, as determining whether information is correct requires being able to extract the relevant data from the source PDFs.

1.5 Approach

To address the first objective, we curated four new datasets from the initial PDF files which could be used for exploratory analyses and training models: 1) A dataset of all PDF pages converted to images. 2) A dataset of PDF file metadata. 3) A dataset of (computer selectable) text directly extracted from the PDFs. 4) A dataset of text generated from the image dataset using optical character recognition (a computer vision technique for identifying characters in images).

In Section 3 we describe in detail how we analysed the metadata dataset and the two text datasets, performing the following streams of work:

- Determining whether an application form can be classified as either hand-written/scanned, or computer-generated and text searchable, using only features in the PDF metadata and simple metrics such as the length of

the text extracted from the PDF. This distinction is important as certain analysis techniques do not work for handwritten or scanned files.

- Comparing text generated with optical character recognition and text directly extracted from the PDF file. We expect to be able to extract text from a greater variety of documents with optical character recognition (as scanned or handwritten documents do not have text embedded in them), but with a lower accuracy than directly extracted text.
- Developing a proof of concept model capable of classifying the type of a file (application form or type of drawing) using only PDF metadata and word counts of its text content. Word counts here refers to the number of occurrences, in a given document, of any of the top 250 words appearing in planning application files.

In Section 4 we focus on planning drawings, where we use the image dataset to classify drawing types. We investigated using a deep learning object detection model to locate different elements within an architectural plan. The model locates and assigns a class label to each object in a planning drawing.

1.6 Main Conclusions

Albeit at a proof of concept stage, our work demonstrates the feasibility of automatically detecting common application errors which relate to required information (either whole documents or parts of documents) not being provided. The remaining common errors refer to whether the provided information is correct, which was out of the scope of this challenge. The main conclusions of our work can be summarised as follows:

- Optical character recognition is capable of extracting accurate typed text from planning documents, matching directly extracted text with around 90% accuracy. It is also more flexible than direct text extraction as it can be used recover information from files without computer-selectable text, such as scanned documents. The model we used is not able to recover handwritten text but this may be possible with future modifications.
- We demonstrate that it is possible to classify the document type from its text content and PDF metadata. Our prototype classifier can distinguish between 5 document categories with 94% accuracy. It may be possible to infer whether a document is in a standard format (for example whether it is handwritten or not) using only its metadata and the first word in the text.
- We train a proof of concept object detection model capable of localising drawings (a file may contain multiple drawings), drawing captions, and true north symbols within architectural plan PDFs. The same approach can be extended to detect other elements mentioned in the common errors, such as missing scales.

1.7 Recommendations and Limitations

Given the time constraints of the challenge all results should be considered preliminary and require full validation. In general we used default parameters for all pre-processing steps and the models we trained, so it is likely that higher accuracies can be achieved with further fine-tuning of the various approaches. For the text-based models, in particular, several other techniques (such as topic analysis or word embeddings) can be used which may be capable of preserving more of the meaning and context of the original text. A key simplification we made was to treat text and image data separately. This meant, for example, treating application forms as unstructured text, and being able to locate a drawing and its caption but not being able to determine the type of drawing from the text in the caption. Future work should aim to combine text- and image-based models.

The biggest difficulty with this challenge is the lack of labelled data. To be able to train the object detection model we manually labelled 30 of the planning drawings in the dataset, but to attain the best possible accuracies hundreds or even thousands of labelled examples would be needed. Creating datasets of processed files (text or images rather than PDFs) with appropriate labels targeted at each of the common planning application errors would be hugely beneficial to any future work. Generating synthetic data or crowdsourcing may be viable ways to quickly create labelled datasets.

2 Data Overview

The dataset consists of planning applications active in the London Borough of Redbridge from 1 January - 30 September 2019. This section describes the structure of the dataset and the initial pre-processing steps that were necessary to convert it into formats more suitable for data science.

2.1 Dataset Description

All planning application documents are publicly available, with private information (generally contact details) redacted. For example, applications in the London Borough of Redbridge are available online in their planning portal [2]. Via agreement with Redbridge and other councils, Agile Datum has access to bulk datasets of applications.

The full dataset used for this project contains 1787 applications, with each application stored in a directory containing all the files associated with it. Each application has around 10 supporting documents, all in PDF format, within which we expect to find at least one document of the following types:

- **Application Forms:** Form containing general information such as the address and a description of work to be done. Some applications may also have other supporting forms. For example, if the property is in a conservation area more details may be required.
- **Site Plans:** Maps of the local neighbourhood including property boundaries and highlighting the extent of the site that the application concerns.
- **Floor Plans:** Architectural drawings of the room layout on each floor of the building before and after the proposed work.
- **Elevations:** Architectural drawings of the exterior faces of the building, from all angles, before and after the proposed work.

Applications also commonly have other types of document associated with them, for example:

- **Letters and other correspondence:** Application outcome notices from the council, objections from local residents, emails between the council and the applicant, and similar.
- **Photographs:** Although not part of a standard application, some applicants submit photographs of the property.
- **Detailed Reports:** Some planning agencies submit detailed reports and justifications for the work to be done.

For example, a typical application contains files similar to the following:

Application-Form.609877.pdf
Photographs.609878.pdf
Combined-Plans.ground-floor.609879.pdf
Combined-Plans.rear-elevations.609880.pdf
Site-Block-Plan.existing-block-plan.609881.pdf
Site-Block-Plan.proposed-block-plan.609882.pdf
Site-Block-Plan.site-plan.609883.pdf

Applications usually contain multiple documents of the same type, for example existing and proposed drawings (before and after the proposed work to be done has been completed as mentioned above). There is also a large variety across documents of the same type. For example, some application forms are digitally generated from a standardised form (vectorised) some are handwritten (scanned, rasterised), and some are generated from an email. Similarly, there is no standard layout for the plans, with different fonts, layouts, and scales.

Moreover, although files in this dataset have meaningful names (i.e. indicative of their contents), there may be other councils with application processes where this is not the case. Therefore, models developed should not rely on the file name being a meaningful indicator of a document's contents.

For this project, the full dataset contains over 17,000 PDF files. Figures 1, 2, 3 and 4 show examples of a typical application form, site plan, floor plan and elevation drawings. Each figure shows the best-case scenario in terms of the ease of interpreting the document computationally. Meaning that all examples shown are in a purely digital format with no handwritten elements and contain only the information or drawings expected to exist in a document of the given type.

2.2 Data Quality Issues

As mentioned, planning applications come in varying forms and contents. There are several issues that make analysing this dataset and using it to develop models more challenging. These are summarised below.

2.2.1 PDF File Format

Machine Learning models typically require images, raw text or some form of tabular data as input, and therefore cannot directly use PDF files. Before any analysis could begin the PDFs had to be converted into different formats (images and text), as described in Section 2.3.

Application forms are perhaps the best example where using nonstandard PDF format leads to difficulties. If form data were available in tabular format the document's structure, i.e. the ability to link questions to responses, is trivially

Planning & Environmental Services
 Royal Hall
 Royal Hall
 1000 High Street, E11 2RH
 London Borough of Redbridge
 Tel: 0208 309 2222
 Fax: 0208 309 2222
 Email: planning@redbridge.gov.uk
 Website: www.redbridge.gov.uk

For Office Use Only
 Date received: _____
 Date sent: _____
 Pre-paid: _____
 Application No: _____

London Borough of Redbridge

Householder Application for Planning Permission for works or extension to a dwelling, Town and Country Planning Act 1990

Publication of applications on planning authority website.
 Please note that the electronic journal of the submission form and its supporting documents may be published on the Authority's website.
 If you require any further clarification, please contact the Authority's planning department.

1. Applicant Name, Address and Contact Details
 Please note that the electronic journal of the submission form and its supporting documents may be published on the Authority's website.
 If you require any further clarification, please contact the Authority's planning department.

Title: _____ First Name: _____ Surname: _____
 Company Name: _____
 Street Address: 27, Woodside Road
 Telephone Number: _____
 Mobile Number: _____
 Town/City: WOODFORD GREEN
 Postcode: IG8 5TW
 County: _____
 E-mail address: _____
 Fax number: _____
 Do you use e-mail (add in e-mail of the applicant)? Yes No

2. Agent Name, Address and Contact Details
 Title: _____ First Name: _____ Surname: _____
 Company Name: LONDON CONSULTANTS LTD.
 Street Address: 80 Southall Road
 Telephone Number: _____
 Mobile Number: _____
 Town/City: WOODFORD
 Postcode: IG8 5LP
 County: United Kingdom
 E-mail address: _____
 Fax number: _____
 Do you use e-mail (add in e-mail of the agent)? Yes No

3. Description of Proposed Works
 Please describe the proposed works:
 LIGHT CONVERSION WITH FACULTY AND A REAR GARDEN AT THE REAR
 Has this work already been carried out without planning permission? Yes No

4. Site Address Details
 Full postal address of the site (including full postcode where available):
 House Number: 27, Address: _____
 Street Address: Woodside Road
 Town/City: WOODFORD GREEN
 Postcode: IG8 5TW
 Description of location of a grid reference (should be included if possible as per below):
 Easting: 543527
 Northing: 100861

5. Pedestrian and Vehicle Access, Roads and Rights of Way
 Is it new or altered vehicle access proposed for or from the public highway? Yes No
 Is a new or altered pedestrian access proposed for or from the public highway? Yes No
 Do the proposed works involve any drainage or other works on a public highway? Yes No

6. Pre-application Advice
 Has assistance in your area been sought from the local authority about this application? Yes No

7. Trees and Hedges
 Are there any trees or hedges on your site (existing or all existing protected trees and hedges) which are to be removed or altered in your proposed development? Yes No
 Are any trees or hedges to be removed or altered in order to carry out your proposal? Yes No

8. Parking
 Will the proposed works affect existing or proposed parking arrangements? Yes No

9. Authority Employee/Member
 Will anyone in your household, firm, or organisation be employed or engaged in any way in the proposed works? Yes No
 Do any of these appointments apply to you? Yes No

10. Site Visit
 Can the site be seen from a public road (public footpath, driveway or other public place)? Yes No

Figure 1: Example pages from an application form

Figure 2: Example of a site plan

Figure 3: Example of a floor plan drawing

Figure 4: Example of an elevations drawing

preserved. In the current PDF formats, this structure is lost and difficult to reconstruct, although some tools exist [3].

2.2.2 Lack of Labelled Data

Training supervised ML models requires labelled data. For example, for a model to be able to learn to detect whether a drawing contains a true north symbol it must be given examples (generally previously annotated by a human) that are known to (or not to) have a true north symbol in them.

In order to develop and validate models in this work, a limited set of labels was created by hand or by parsing file names (Section 3.3.2).

2.2.3 Non-standard Files per Application

The files present in each planning application differ. This is best understood via an example. Below are the files corresponding to two different applications:

APPLICATION 1

Application-Form.609877.pdf
Photographs.609878.pdf
Combined-Plans.ground-floor.609879.pdf
Combined-Plans.rear-elevations.609880.pdf
Site-Block-Plan.existing-block-plan.609881.pdf
Site-Block-Plan.proposed-block-plan.609882.pdf
Site-Block-Plan.site-plan.609883.pdf

APPLICATION 2

Application-Form.613971.pdf
Supporting-Documents.Planning-Statement.613961.pdf
Site-Block-Plan.Site-location.613962.pdf
Site-Block-Plan.Block.613963.pdf
Combined-Plans.Ground-floor.613964.pdf
Combined-Plans.Roof.613965.pdf
Existing-Plans.Front-elevations.613966.pdf
Proposed-Plans.Front-elevations.613967.pdf
Existing-Plans.Side-A-and-B-elevations.613968.pdf
Proposed-Plans.Side-A-and-B-elevations.613969.pdf
Proposed-Plans.Section.613970.pdf
Decision-Notice.621791.pdf
Decision-Notice.Decision-notice.621794.pdf

In APPLICATION 1, the existing and proposed plans for the ground floor and rear elevations are in the same document, but the existing and proposed site plans

are in separate documents. In APPLICATION 2, the ground floor plans are still in the same document, but existing and proposed plans are split into multiple documents for the elevations. Furthermore, between the applications, the plan types are not standard: APPLICATION 1 has only a rear elevation plan, whereas APPLICATION 2 has elevations for the front and sides A and B. For this reason, identifying the relevant existing and proposed plans is not straightforward.

2.2.4 Non-standard Application Forms

While each application contains exactly one application form, these documents come in many different PDF formats. These include:

- Computer-generated, vectorised, text-searchable.
- Computer-generated but subsequently scanned or rasterised, not text-searchable.
- Hand-written and scanned, rasterised, not-text searchable.

Furthermore, the application forms come in different layouts. Some are forms downloaded from the Borough of Redbridge website, whereas some are printed from emails. Hand-written forms have a different layout than computer generated ones. Figure 5 shows an example snippet from a handwritten form, which contains mostly the same information as the computer-generated form in Figure 1 but in a different layout.

2.2.5 Non-Standard Drawings

The PDFs that contain drawings are not standardised either. They may contain one or multiple drawings with different layouts (e.g. location of titles and other metadata). Some are rotated 90 degrees. They also vary in scale, colours, positioning, and labelling. Text and labels do not have a specific format, varying in dimensions, positioning, captioning and font. Symbols (e.g. true north) and scales also come in many different styles.

Figure 6 shows a submitted planning drawing that is mostly handwritten, but also contains a mixture of floor plans, site plans and elevations. This differs from the computer-generated plan in Figure 3, which contains only a single drawing.

2.3 Data Pre-processing

From the initial dataset of PDF files we curated four new datasets more suitable for prototyping ML models: two datasets of raw text extracted from the documents in different ways, a dataset of PDF metadata, and an image dataset, as described below.

5. Description of Proposed Works (continued)

Has the work already started? Yes No
 If Yes, please state when the work was started (DD/MM/YYYY): _____ (Date must be pre-application submission)
 Has the work already been completed? Yes No
 If Yes, please state when the work was completed (DD/MM/YYYY): _____ (Date must be pre-application submission)

4. Site Address Details

Please provide the full postal address of the application site.

Site: House number: 70 House type: _____
 House name: _____
 Address 1: CHELMSFORD ROAD
 Address 2: _____
 Town: SOUTH LINDFORD
 Country: ENGLAND
 Postcode (optional): EC2R 2AR

5. Pedestrian and Vehicle Access, Roads and Rights of Way

Is a new or altered vehicle access proposed to or from the public highway? Yes No
 Is a new or altered pedestrian access proposed to or from the public highway? Yes No
 Do the proposals require any dimensions, stipulations and/or restrictions of public rights of way? Yes No
 If Yes to any questions, please show details on your plans or drawings and state the reference number(s) of the plan(s)/drawing(s): _____

6. Pre-application Advice

Has assistance or prior advice been sought from the local authority about this application? Yes No
 If Yes, please complete the following information about the advice you were given. (This will help the authority to deal with this application more efficiently).
 Please tick if the full correct details are not known, and then complete as much as possible:
 Officer name: _____
 Address: _____
 Date (DD/MM/YYYY): _____
 Contact for pre-application submission: _____
 Details of the pre-application advice received: _____

7. Trees and Hedges

Are there any trees or hedges on your own property or on adjoining properties, which are within falling distance of your proposed development? Yes No
 If Yes, please mark their position on a suitable plan and state the reference number of any plan(s) or drawing(s): _____
 Will any trees or hedges need to be removed or pruned in order to carry out your proposal? Yes No
 If Yes, please show on your plans which trees the pruning requires e.g. T1, T2 etc, state the reference number of the plan(s) drawing(s) and indicate the scale: _____

8. Parking

Will the proposed works affect existing car parking arrangements? Yes No
 If Yes, please describe: THE LORS OF ONE OFF STREET PARKING SPACE & ONE TWO SPACES REMAIN.

9. Authority Employees / Member

With respect to the Authority I am:
 (a) a member of staff Or any of these statements apply to you?
 (b) an elected member
 (c) related to a member of staff
 (d) related to an elected member
 If Yes, please provide details of the name, relationship and job: _____

Figure 5: Example page from a scanned handwritten application form.

Figure 6: Example of a planning document containing hand drawn floor plans, elevations and a site plan.

Note that, given the time constraints of the challenge, we did not attempt to extract structured information (key-value pairs) from forms and instead converted whole document contents into plain text. This data is still valuable for training models, as seen in Section 3.3.2.

2.3.1 Image Dataset

Using the python library `pdf2image` [4], we converted every page of each PDF file into a separate PNG image to be used for computer vision purposes, such as the object detection model developed in Section 4.

2.3.2 Direct Text Extraction

The text in original, computer filled PDFs with selectable text (as opposed to scans or handwritten documents) is embedded in the file and can be extracted directly. The python library `PyPDF2` [5] is used to extract all the text in each PDF.

2.3.3 PDF Metadata

PDF files contain metadata, such as author, title, or the utility which has produced the PDF file. This information can be useful in determining the type of document, such as determining whether a PDF file is the scan of a paper application, or if it is a computer filled application which has then been converted to an image but in a PDF, via a conversion utility. This is discussed in Section 3.1. PDF metadata was also extracted using the `PyPDF2` [5].

2.3.4 Text Extraction via Optical Character Recognition

Direct text extraction fails for scanned documents or files with unselectable text. In this case the computer vision technique known as optical character recognition (OCR) is used to (attempt to) recover text. OCR tools take an image as input, recognise text characters within it, and produce plain text as output.

A popular open-source OCR library is `Tesseract` [6], currently developed by Google. We used `Tesseract v4` (released in 2019), which introduces an LSTM neural network architecture for improved accuracy, particularly in locating lines of text [7], and its Python wrapper `pytesseract` [8].

`Tesseract` works well for typed text but generally not for handwritten text, which requires a more complex model and open-source solutions are not as readily available. The accuracy and benefits of `Tesseract` on this dataset are discussed in Section 3.2.

2.4 Recommendations

The data challenges (unstructured data, non-ideal file formats, lack of labels etc.) experienced here are common in many data science projects, leading to as much of 80% of a data scientist's time being spent cleaning or sourcing data [9]. In this case, the data quality could be greatly improved for machine learning purposes by some of the following:

- **Standardising application forms:** Enforce that applicants enter information on a standard form. Ideally, this would be digital with the entered data stored in a database. Machine-readable, tabular data could then be easily queried and extracted without the need for the (information-lossy) reading of PDFs. If this is impossible, even a standard PDF format with standard layout would make reading the data significantly easier.
- **Standardising planning drawings:** Enforce a common standard in the layout of planning drawings. This may include:
 - Allowing a maximum of one drawing per document.
 - Enforcing existing and proposed plans to be in separate documents.
 - Standardising the layout and included types of annotations, metadata and symbols.
 - Using standard filenames that clearly indicate the document contents.

We acknowledge that planning applications are complex and little can be done to retrospectively change the format of historic data. Nevertheless, any movement in the direction of standardised infrastructure and stricter regulation on the composition and contents of application documents would be hugely beneficial. This would ease the pathway for future work in developing AI capable of answering more nuanced questions, and may be more cost effective than developing high-level AI tools to parse a nonstandard dataset that is not easily machine-readable.

3 Text and Metadata Analyses

This section describes analyses performed on the two text datasets (text directly extracted from the PDF and via optical character recognition) and PDF metadata. The work focuses on two aims:

- 1) Classify a document as either handwritten/scanned or computer-generated and text searchable, using only features in the PDF metadata and simple metrics such as the length of extracted text. Although this does not directly answer any of the overall challenge goals, it is a valuable initial step needed to determine the viable analysis techniques for a given document.
- 2) Classify a document (form or drawing type) from its text content. Many common errors in applications relate to certain documents not being provided, thus an automated approach to determine which documents have been submitted would address many of the challenge goals.

3.1 Directly Extracted PDF Text and Metadata

This section uses data extracted directly from the PDF files (text content and file metadata) with the PyPDF2 package (Section 2.3.1). We concentrate on application forms only. These were filtered from the full dataset by identifying file names with a format like `Application-Form.661779.pdf`. Out of the 1787 applications we were able to successfully extract application form data from 1771 of them.

The results presented are exploratory analyses using features such as:

- Number of pages
- Length of text extracted
- First word extracted
- File size
- Rasterised image content
- PDF producer/generation tool

The overall goal is to investigate whether simple metrics or rule-based systems can be used to identify how an application form has been generated (computer-filled, hand-filled then scanned, or computer-filled then scanned).

3.1.1 PDF Length and File Size

We first conduct sanity checks on the number of pages in the application forms. The standard computer-filled application form (like Figure 1) is four pages long.

Figure 7 shows that the most common application form length in our dataset, as given by the PDF metadata, is indeed four pages as expected.

Similarly, we manually check the text length of several forms and found them to have around 5000 characters. Figure 8 shows the distribution of the length of text (number of characters) in the data we extracted by processing the original PDFs. Different colours correspond to different first words in the document, which is discussed in the next section. The majority of forms have a similar text length to what we expect, typically between 5000 to 7000 characters.

However, for 264 of the forms almost no text is extracted. These will be referred to as NULL files. For these files the text content is either empty or consists only of repeated new lines or whitespace, such as `\n\n\n\n\n`. They correspond to PDF files which are pure rasters, i.e. scans. The number of new line characters is related to the number of pages in the original PDF file, and the number of images making up the PDF file.

NULL files are either scans of computer-filled application forms or scans of hand-filled application forms. One way to distinguish between the two cases may be to look at the PDF file size, as shown for all forms in Figure 9. The largest NULL file (grouped at text length zero on the horizontal axis) has a file size over 100 times greater than the smallest NULL file. Most non-null files have a file size of around 400 kB (4×10^5 bytes), and all files larger than 2000 kB are NULL files. It may be that larger file sizes correspond to hand-filled forms, as they contain more image-like content, but we did not have time to investigate this further.

3.1.2 First word of text content

We also looked into whether the first word appearing in the text of the application form conveys information about its source.

There were 45 distinct first words in the text directly extracted from the 1771 application forms. Out of the 45 words, 7 were the first word in at least 60 of the forms, as shown in Table 1 (where NULL files are categorised as one type of first word):

Figure 7: Distribution of number of pages in planning application forms.

Figure 8: Distribution of the length of text directly extracted from application form PDFs. Different colours indicate different first words.

Figure 9: PDF file size versus length of text extracted for application forms. Different colours indicate different first words

First Word	Count
Application	680
Householder	422
NULL	264
Version	130
Form	99
From:redbridge.developers@red	61
Notification	60

Table 1: First word appearing in application forms.

Other first words have fewer than four occurrences and were ignored for the rest of the analysis. Figure 10 shows boxplots of the length of the application forms separated according to their first word.

From inspection, files where the first word is **Application** correspond to computer-filled application forms. Alternatively, files starting with **From:redbridge.developers@red** correspond to forms sent in the bodies of emails and later converted to PDFs, for example. Files where the first word is **Notification** correspond to the small cluster of points with text length around 2,000 and file size around 3,000 in Figure 9.

It seems that first word alone could be a useful feature in classifying the type of application form, but further work is needed to investigate this. Alternatively, Section 3.3.2 explores using word counts from the whole text content.

3.1.3 PDF Producer

Text analysis looks promising but what can be done for the 264 NULL documents where text extraction failed? One approach is to use text extracted by optical character recognition (Section 2.3.4). Another hypothesis is that the metadata of the PDF can help in predicting which application forms are scans of hand-filled forms and which are computer generated forms which have then been converted. In particular, the field **/Producer** in the metadata gives some indication of the type of software or hardware that was used to generate the PDF.

Within the NULL application forms there are around 50 different producers, as shown in Table 2. Out of the producers “Adobe PSL for Canon” and “HP Scan Extended” are related to tools used with scanners, so are likely to be hand-written documents. Alternatively, “Acrobat Distiller” and “Microsoft Print to PDF” are tools used to convert electronic files into PDF format. However, further analysis is needed to verify that this intuition holds, as a scanned hand-written document could initially be produced as an image and then be converted to PDF with one of the file conversion tools, for example.

3.1.4 PDF Image Content Metadata

Another set of metadata that may be meaningful for classifying different types of application form is nature of the rasterised image content in the PDF. A scanned form may be represented as single page sized images in the PDF, whereas a computer-generated form may contain many smaller objects corresponding to each form element, for example.

For each PDF document we extracted and calculated the following quantities related to their rasterised image content:

- Number of images.

Figure 10: Boxplots of the length of the extracted text for each of the seven most common first words appearing in application forms.

PDF Producer	Count
Acrobat Distiller 15.0 (Windows)	51
Microsoft: Print To PDF	38
Onstream Trapeze 8.548	35
Adobe PSL 1.2e for Canon	28
?	18
HP Scan Extended Application	7
Adobe PSL 1.1e for Canon	5
<i>Other (<5 each)</i>	53
<i>None provided</i>	30

Table 2: Most common values of the Producer field in application form meta-data.

- Page size of the PDF document.
- Total area taken up by the rasterised PDF content/images.
- Image centroid per document page.

Figures 11 and 12 show the average image area and count per PDF page respectively. Some outliers with high areas/counts are not shown and further studies could be done to understand how these extreme situations arise. For the image area in particular there are several distinct groups of forms centred around different averages.

Figure 13 (left) shows the average image area per page plotted against the length of text extracted from the PDF document. In Figure 13 (left) we clearly see two different regimes: - Documents with very little text extracted (NULL files), with a large spread in average image area per page. - Documents with low average image area per page, but a large spread in text length.

The right plot in Figure 13 again shows that there appears to be several clusters of application form types. However, more work is needed to understand what type of document belongs to which cluster.

3.1.5 Conclusions

In this section we have selected the PDF files containing application forms and performed exploratory analyses on the text and metadata we were able to directly extract from them.

Looking at the first word in the extracted text already appears to be enough to give a rough idea of how the form may have been generated. However, it was not possible to directly extract any text from 274 out of the 1771 forms, we referred to these as NULL forms. The NULL forms are either computer-filled applications which were then converted to an image, or scans of hand-filled applications. Looking at the distribution of the PDF file size alone is not enough to discriminate between these two possibilities. Instead, we propose to look at the metadata contained in the PDF file.

Figure 11: Distribution of average image area on each application form page.

Figure 12: Distribution of number of images on each application form page.

Figure 13: Average image area per PDF page vs. length of text extracted, where the right is a zoomed in version of the left.

It appears that the `Producer` field in the metadata may be a simple and effective piece of information to understand how an application form (or a PDF file in general), has been created, particularly if it directly refers to a scanner. We also began to look at other parts of the metadata, such as the document's image content. It is highly likely that taking into account the other fields in the metadata will refine our understanding of the application process and should be exploited.

We have not had time to exploit more of the text information (of the non-NULL application forms). There are only a few first words, and inspecting the files should reveal a simple rule to classify them. Alternatively, approaches using the full text content can be attempted, as described for the text extracted via optical character recognition in the next section.

3.2 Text Extracted with Optical Character Recognition

In this section we explore the dataset of text extracted from the PDF documents after being converted to images and then processed with optical character recognition (OCR, see Section 2.3.4). Compared to text extracted directly from the original PDFs we expect the OCR text to have lower accuracy, but with the benefit of being able to recover text from a larger fraction of the documents (e.g. scanned files where direct text extraction is not possible).

3.2.1 Length

The simplest way to compare the directly extracted and OCR text datasets is to look at their lengths. Figure 14 shows a scatter plot of the application form text lengths for the two datasets.

The majority of the documents lay on or close to the diagonal where the lengths of the OCR text and the directly extracted text are approximately equal. This group contains documents with digitised text where direct text extraction is successful, and it appears that OCR recovers a similar amount of text for these files.

A second group of documents lies along the horizontal axis, the scanned files where it has not been possible to extract text directly (the NULL files). However, OCR has been able to recover up to 25000 characters of text for these files. This demonstrates that OCR is a promising tool to extract information from files that are submitted with more difficult formats to process.

A small number of documents lie outside these two groups, where text has successfully been extracted in both cases but with different lengths. The cause of this should be investigated further. One hypothesis is that files with lower OCR text length than expected may be rotated to an incorrect orientation, making image processing more difficult.

Figure 14: Scatter plot comparing the text length (number of characters) in data extracted from application forms directly and with OCR.

3.2.2 String Difference Metrics

Although the OCR text has similar length to the directly extracted text in most cases this doesn't guarantee that they both have the same information. OCR is more prone to misinterpreting characters in the image and may return text with many errors, for example. To verify that the OCR text contains the same content we calculated several string distance metrics.

Here we present the results of calculating the Levenshtein distance [10] between the OCR text and the directly extracted text. The Levenshtein distance between two strings is defined as the minimum number of operations required to make one string match the other. Allowed operations are to insert, delete or change a single character in the string. For example, the Levenshtein distance between “coat” and “court” is two, where the required operations are:

- Operation 1: Replace “a” with “u”: coat -> cout
- Operation 2: Insert “r”: cout -> court

A Levenshtein distance of 0 means the two strings are identical. We also calculated the Damerau-Levenshtein [11] and Jaro-Winkler [12] distances, which modify the Levenshtein distance by using different weightings and sets of permissible operations, but found them to give similar results and do not present them here.

As the Levenshtein distance is a raw count of operations it tends to give larger values for longer strings. To be able to compare documents with different lengths we calculated a Levenshtein distance ratio, R , as follows:

$$R = L / \max(T_{ocr}, T_{direct})$$

Where L is the Levenshtein distance, T_{ocr} is the length of the text extracted with OCR, and T_{direct} is the length of the text directly extracted from the PDF. Documents where one of the text datasets has zero length and the other is non-zero have a ratio of 1.

Figure 15a shows a violin plot of the Levenshtein ratio across all PDF files, including application forms, drawings and other document types. Violin plots combine a box plot with a kernel density plot, allowing the full distribution of the data to be observed [13].

The distribution of the Levenshtein ratio is bimodal. The peak close to a ratio of 1.0 corresponds to scans, photographs and other non-standard document formats where one of the text extraction methods fails, or is only able to reproduce a small fraction of the source text. Scanned documents with typed text lie in this peak as OCR is able to detect the writing but nothing can be directly extracted, for example.

Alternatively, the peak centred near a ratio of 0.1 corresponds to cases where both extraction methods produced similar text, both in terms of length and in the actual characters and words they contain. Figure 15b shows the Levenshtein distance plotted for application forms only and excluding cases where direct text extraction failed. In this case only a single peak with mean ratio $R = 0.11 \pm 0.05$ remains, meaning around 9 out of every 10 characters is the same in the two sets of extracted text.

3.2.3 Comparison of OCR and Directly Extracted Text

For several of the application forms with poor matches between the OCR and directly extracted text ($R > 0.15$) we used `git diff` [14] to visually compare the two and identify the ways in which each method can go wrong.

Figure 16 shows an example of this for a small snippet of one form. The most common error in the directly extracted text (green) is missing newlines or spaces between words. For example, the last two questions in the form snippet have line breaks between “natural” and “ground”, and “the” and “natural” respectively, but these are extracted as the single words “naturalground” and “thenatural”.

Alternatively, the computer vision approach used in the OCR text has a tendency to misinterpret characters. Examples in Figure 16 include “extend” becoming “exxend”, and “externally from” becoming “exbemqly trim”. There are also cases of missing spaces between words in the OCR text.

3.2.4 Conclusions

Using optical character recognition (OCR) we were able to recover text from many of the documents where direct text extraction fails due to them not having selectable text (scanned forms, for example). For documents where both

(a) For all planning application PDFs.

(b) For planning application forms, excluding forms where one of the text extraction methods failed.

Figure 15: Levenshtein distance ratios between directly- and OCR- extracted text.

Figure 16: a) Snippet from an application form. b) Result of git diff on text extracted directly and with OCR for this form snippet. Directly extracted text is highlighted in green, OCR output in red, and white where both agree.

approaches are possible there is good agreement between the two sets of extracted text, with an average of 0.11 ± 0.05 differences per character. As OCR is able to recover text from a larger range of documents, albeit with some inaccuracies, we would recommend this approach, either on its own or in combination with directly extracted text.

Tesseract, which we used to perform OCR, is trained to detect typed text and therefore we were unable to extract information from handwritten files. However, interpreting handwritten text is an active area of research [15] so with further work it may also be able to extract data from these files.

3.3 Classifying Document Type from Text and Metadata

In this section we show a proof of concept of a pipeline that could be used to classify the type of a document from its text content (generated by OCR) and PDF metadata. We focused on the text extracted by OCR here, as it works for a larger variety of document types, but the same approach could be used for directly extracted text (or a combination of the two).

3.3.1 Cleaning of Extracted Text

The text extraction from the PDFs (both direct extraction and via OCR) produces unstructured, messy text files for each document in the application (both forms and drawings). Examples of issues in the extracted text data include:

- Many blank lines.
- Nonsense character strings (e.g. `aaaaaazzzfvregaaaaa`).
- Incorrect groupings of characters (e.g. `doc um ent`).
- Incorrect spellings.

To be useful for training models these text files must be cleaned, leaving only the semantically correct and relevant data, and then converted into a numeric format suitable for a model input. For cleaning the text we used python string operations, regex expressions, and the Python Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) [16] to perform the following steps:

- Convert all text to lowercase.
- Remove all digits and punctuation.
- Remove all whitespace (apart from spaces between words).
- Remove common words (e.g. “that”, “because”, “have”)
- Perform lemmatisation, e.g. replacing plurals with the singular equivalent (documents to document).

- Remove words with fewer than 4 characters.
- Remove words that appear in fewer than 10 percent of documents.

The main assumption of the steps above is that we will be attempting to classify documents based on counts of the words they contain alone, not on the grammar or ordering of those words. In this context capitalisation, punctuation and numeric values convey no meaning so can be removed. Common words, like “the”, will appear in almost every block of text so can also be removed as they are unlikely to be useful in distinguishing one type of document from another.

The lemmatisation step aims to convert different forms of the same word to their base form, for example replacing “houses” with “house”. We used the NLTK implementation of WordNet lemmatiser [16] with default values to do this. This tends to leave many words unchanged, for example “proposed” is left unchanged rather than becoming “propose”, and could be improved with customised arguments or using a more modern model such as those provided by spaCy [17].

The final step of removing infrequent words is used to reduce an initial vocabulary of tens of thousands of words to the top 250 words that appear across all types of planning application documents in our dataset. This was chosen to give a reasonable number of features as input to our baseline model, but should be fine-tuned with future work.

The top 250 words are shown in the word cloud in Figure 17. This gives a quick sanity check of the OCR and cleaning process, as the largest words, such as “site”, “planning” and “development”, all clearly have associations with planning applications.

3.3.2 Model Inputs and Class Labels

To convert the cleaned text into numeric values that can be used as input to a model we used term frequency-inverse document frequency (tf-idf) vectors [18], specifically the scikit-learn implementation [19]. For each word in each document its tf-idf value depends on the number of occurrences of the word in the document normalised by the fraction of documents that contain the given word. This gives increased weighting to less common words (which may be more meaningful in determining the document type) compared to using raw word counts.

We combined these vectors with the results of previous text analyses to create three sets of features:

- **Word Content:** tf-idf values for the top 250 words appearing in the cleaned OCR text (from Section 3.3.1).
- **OCR Metrics:** Length, Levenshtein ratio and other metrics related to the OCR text (from Section 3.2).

many, typically shallow, decision trees, and implementations have given state of the art performance in many usecases [21]. CatBoost specifically claims to achieve high accuracy without extensive parameter tuning, is quick to train, and has in-built support for categorical features. Future work should investigate whether CatBoost is the best choice or if other algorithms give better performance.

3.3.4 Results

We computed the classification accuracy for CatBoost models trained separately with each of the three sets of features, and a final model with all the features combined. In each case we used a 75%-25% train-test split with the same random seed set, yielding the following accuracies on the test set:

- **PDF Metadata:** 50% accuracy
- **OCR Metrics:** 60% accuracy
- **Word Content:** 80% accuracy
- **Combined:** 94% accuracy

For the model using the combined set of features we also calculated the F1-score [22], which is the harmonic mean of the precision and recall: $F_1 = 2 \times (\text{precision} \times \text{recall}) / (\text{precision} + \text{recall})$. The above applies when considering a single document class, we used micro-averaging of the results across all classes (weighting each class by its number of occurrences) to get a single-valued metric. The F1-score can be more meaningful than accuracy in cases where there are imbalanced classes. The F1-score on the test set is 0.95 for our combined model.

Feature importance methods can be used to identify which inputs (features) in a given model are contributing the most to the decisions a model makes. We used the default CatBoost feature importance algorithm, `PredictionValuesChange`, which represents how much a prediction changes on average if a feature value changes [23]. Figure 18 shows the top 10 features with the highest importance values in the combined model. As you would expect, some of the words that appear are clearly associated with drawings (e.g. “drawing”, “scale”, “plan”), whilst others are more associated with details appearing on forms (e.g. “telephone”, “application”, “description”).

3.3.5 Conclusions

We cleaned the OCR text and converted it to tf-idf vectors for the top 250 words appearing across application files of all types in our dataset. Using these vectors, combined with metadata about the OCR text and the original PDF, we trained a CatBoost classifier to predict whether a file contained a form, proposed drawings, existing drawings, combined proposed and existing drawings, or a

Figure 18: Top 10 features with the highest feature importance. “Text length” refers to the length of the extracted text, all other features refer to the appearance of the given word in the document.

different document type. This model achieved an accuracy of 94% on the test dataset. Based on these results we believe it is feasible to classify the type of each file in an application based solely on its text content and metadata relating to the original PDF file. This would solve the challenge questions relating to automatically validating whether all supporting files have been uploaded with an application.

Future work could include:

- Extending the document categories to include more meaningful types, such as “site plan”, “block plan” and “floor plan”.
- Using a combination of directly extracted and OCR text, whichever gives the best results for a given document.
- Using an improved lemmatisation algorithm as part of the text cleaning process.
- Tuning the number of words included as features in the model, and/or including bigrams or trigrams (pairs or triplets of words) rather than counts of individual words only.
- Tuning the hyperparameters of CatBoost and comparing its results with other algorithms.

4 Image Analyses on Planning Drawings

As mentioned earlier, many planning applications are rejected due to missing components in the drawings, such as missing north symbols, scales, and proposed or original plans. In light of this, we investigated the possibility of using Machine Learning to automatically detect whether a drawing may or may not contain elements such as these. The task of the proposed model is that of object detection: locating the presence of objects in an image, and drawing bounding boxes around each instance of the class.

This section describes the work done on the dataset of PDF pages converted to images, for which we considered only planning drawings and not application forms. We provide evidence showing the promise of deep learning towards detecting useful components in planning drawings.

4.1 Training an Object Detection Deep Learning Model

Deep learning models have shown great capabilities in many computer vision tasks in the past decade, including and certainly not limited to object detection (see Figure 19 for examples of common computer vision tasks). Unfortunately, these models often require vast quantities of labelled data. Given the time restriction of the data study group, we utilise the approach of transfer learning to obtain a suitable deep learning model capable of object detection. We use a state-of-the-art neural network architecture that has been pre-trained on large visual datasets in order to recognise features of images, and fine tune the network to our specific problem domain.

4.1.1 Initial Attempt

We first attempted to use the TensorFlow object detection API, and followed the tutorial “Creating your own Object detector” by Gilbert Tanner [25]. Whilst reaching the stage of training a pre-trained model, we found the API to be out of date, with simple TensorFlow internal operations including loading the model after training deprecated in addition to TensorFlow’s notebook tutorial for using the objection detection API. We decided to look into alternative libraries and settled upon the Mask-RCNN [26] library using Keras [27]. We describe the full process of this below, starting with the need to label the data.

4.1.2 Creating a Training Dataset

Given that we had no labelled data, the first step was to label the images to create the training dataset. This required manually drawing bounding boxes

Figure 19: Common computer vision tasks: image classification, object detection and instance segmentation [24].

around the objects we wanted the model to learn to predict. We used `labelImg` [28] to label the images.

There were several difficulties associated with labelling the images. The rasterised pdfs are messy, with different formats, and can contain several drawings which might even be overlapping. The drawings can also differ in colour (some are in black and white, whilst others are in bright colours) and style.

The following types of drawings can be found in the rasterised pdfs: floor plans, elevation drawings, sections (optional) and site plans. However, categorisation of these is not trivial because there is no specified template or standard practise for drawings in planning applications. Figure 20 below shows an example (unlabelled) drawing plan from an application.

Captions (for each drawing such as “Proposed plan” and “Original plan”) and general text on the application can be easily confused by deep learning models. However, this is especially important for the current context: in order to reject an application for not having both a proposed and original plan, the model needs to be able to identify the caption beneath a drawing separately from general text, even though the two might look very similar. To solve this, we labelled the following objects in each planning application:

- **drawing:** (this can be specified into a particular type of drawing, such as floor plan or block plan, in future experiments)
- **drawingtitle:** (this is the caption below a drawing, specifying whether the drawing is proposed or original/existing)
- **blocktitle:** (this is text we consider as general to the application and is often positioned at the side of the application)
- **north:** (to detect if a north symbol is found in a plan)

Figure 20: Example drawing plan (unlabelled raw image).

Figure 21 shows examples of the process of labelling these classes within `labelImg`. The image is exported in a `.jpg` while the metadata for the labelling (i.e. the coordinates of the bounding box) are exported in a `.xml` format. It's also important to note that we only chose a small subset of objects to detect as a proof of concept but this could easily be extended with further classes in the future.

4.1.3 Training

As mentioned earlier, we used Keras to implement the pipeline and further train and fine tune the model. Keras is a deep learning library which provides a package called `mrcnn` which is based on the Mask-RCNN architecture for object detection and segmentation (explained in section below). We also use `scikit-image` [29] for the image processing.

The current versions that are tested to be compatible are the following:

- Python 3.7
- Tensorflow-gpu 1.14
- Keras 2.3.1
- scikit-image 0.6.2

Figure 21: Example images labelled using labelImg.

- Mask-rcnn 2.1
- CUDA 10.00
- CudNN 7.6.5 (for CUDA 10)

We used an Azure NC-12 virtual machine [30] (with 12 cores, 112 GiB RAM, 2 Tesla K80 GPUs) within a Turing Safe Haven environment [31]. Our code for this experiment was based on Jason Brownlee’s tutorial [32]. The setup and installation instructions are specified in the referenced article.

4.1.4 Mask-RCNN Model Architecture

The Mask R-CNN architecture [33] is basically an extension of Faster R-CNN architecture [34], an architecture used widely for object detection tasks. Whilst for a given image Faster R-CNN returns the class label and bounding box coordinates for each object in the image, Mask R-CNN also generates a segmentation mask (a binary mask that indicates the pixels where the object is in the bounding box). We decided that this might be a useful output that could potentially be utilised in the future for more specific analysis of the images. The Mask R-CNN also has a couple of additional improvements that make it much more accurate, which can be found in their paper.

4.1.5 Validation

Given the time restrictions, we have been unable to perform extensive validation of the model and its training. We minimally use mean average precision (mAP), a standard metric used to evaluate object detection, and visual inspection of the models predictions on the test set to investigate its performance in order to provide support for the proof of concept. We also provide recommendations for further improvements to the model later.

Average precision computes the average precision value for recall value over 0 to 1. Intersection over union (IoU) is used to give an overall decision of whether the prediction was overall correct or not, according to a threshold value for the area of the ground truth and predicted boundaries of the class (see Figure 22).

4.2 Results

We trained the model using the default parameters specified by the Keras model and have not yet optimised hyperparameters. In addition, we were only able to label around 30 images given the timeframe.

Figures 23 and 24 provide example predictions made by the model on two test images and on two training images respectively. The left image in each of these pairs is the ground truth for that example (the bounding box that was labelled

Figure 22: Diagram representation of precision, recall and intersection over union (IoU) [35]

by the human) and the image on the right is the model's predicted bounding boxes. Each class is represented by a different colour.

4.3 Conclusions and Recommendations

In this section, we have provided a proof of concept for deep learning techniques to detect the elements within the drawing plans within a planning application. So far, these elements include the north sign, general drawings, drawing titles and block titles, however the model could be further trained to predict more classes such as scale bars.

4.3.1 Allocation of Labels to Drawings

Since the model shows initial results of detecting both drawings and their captions, one aspect that this experiment enables is the correlation of drawing captions with each drawing. Note that the model as so far is interpreting the caption as an image of the text. However, by drawing a bounding box around the caption the model provides us with coordinates of where the captions are and subsequent techniques such as OCR can be performed to extract the textual content of the caption.

One of the problems of non-standardised planning drawings formats, is that the labels can vary in size, position and content. That makes them hard to read, as a label can be found in between two drawings and there may be uncertainty in to which drawing may belong to.

The solution we found for this problem, is to create one pool with the detected drawings data. and one pool with the detected labelled data. Then find the centroid of these objects, and find the labels that are closest to the drawings. As some drawings can be densely distributed in a page and may have more than one labels allocated to them, we start by finding the drawing that has only one label allocated to it. This label is then removed from the label pool, then we

(a) Example where all objects have been correctly identified, but with some inaccuracies in the bounding boxes.

(b) Example where it has incorrectly predicted two drawings to be on top of other another on this instance of drawing.

Figure 23: Output of predictions made by the object detection model on test images. Ground truth labels are shown on the left and predictions on the right.

(a) Example where most of the objects have been correctly identified.

(b) Example where the model has drawn a bounding box around some of the drawing and then incorrectly identified another part of the drawing as something else.

Figure 24: Output of predictions made by the object detection model on training images. Ground truth labels are shown on the left and predictions on the right.

continue with the next drawing that has only one label assigned to it, and so forth (see Figure 25).

Taken together, this allows automatic pre-processing of planning application drawings that returns the drawings outlined in the image with a corresponding caption. This would then give insights into an application has a north sign (if appropriate), scale bars, and both proposed and original drawings provided for example.

4.3.2 Improving the Deep Learning Model

There are many aspects that could improve the model's performance but just to mention a few:

- Labelling more training data: Our entire dataset was comprised of 30 examples.
- Hyperparameter optimisation: We used the default values of hyperparameters.
- Visualisation of training logging metrics.
- Inclusion of further evaluation metrics such as localisation recall precision (LRP).

4.3.3 Image Segmentation

An alternative approach to detecting components in the drawings in planning applications is *image segmentation*, instead of classical object detection. Image segmentation is the task of clustering patches of an image together which belong to the same class (see Figure 26). In the simplest case, this kind of segmentation could involve using a pre-trained computer vision model to generate a representation or *feature vector* for each patch in the image. Then, after clustering these vectors, one might expect that patches of the image containing similar objects (and therefore similar feature vectors) would appear in the same clusters. This has the advantage of requiring no further training or fine tuning a model.

Figure 25: Drawings and labels are extracted as two separate categories, and then the centroid of each object detection box is used to define the closest label to the drawing.

Figure 26: Examples of image segmentation [36]

5 Conclusions and Future work

In this report, we explore approaches for the automatic detection of common errors in planning applications. Currently, manual validation of such applications consumes 250,000 person days of administration annually and generates frustrating delays for citizens. Many common errors relate to a failure to supply required information, and detecting these errors were the main focus of our work.

The analysed data consists of PDFs from 1787 applications active in the London Borough of Redbridge from 1st January - 30th September 2019. An average application contains 10 PDF files in many different types (e.g. forms, floor plans, site plans or elevations) without any common format. The three main results from this investigation are:

- A range of approaches that can be used to preprocess the PDFs and convert them into formats suitable for training models. These were used to generate four datasets - images of PDF pages, PDF metadata, text directly extracted from the PDFs, and text generated by optical character recognition.
- A CatBoost classifier capable of distinguishing between five different document types with 94% accuracy. As input it uses PDF metadata and cleaned OCR text converted into word count vectors for the top 250 words appearing across Redbridge planning application documents of all types.
- A proof of concept object detection model based on the Mask-RCNN architecture capable of localising drawings, drawing captions, and true north symbols within architectural plans.

5.1 Challenge Questions

Here we review the original challenge questions (the common errors made in planning applications), and to what extent we believe the detection of them is solved or solvable with the approaches described in this report.

Solvable with the approaches in the current work:

- *Are floor plans provided?*
- *Have existing & proposed elevations been provided?*
- *Are block/site plans provided?*
- *Are all scales provided?*
- *Is true north provided?*

These questions consider whether a piece of information is present, but not whether it is correct. We demonstrate the possibility of classifying a document

from its text content (Section 3.3) and identifying elements within a single drawing file (Section 4). In combination these can answer all the questions above.

Feasible with extensions to the current work:

- *Have all supporting files been uploaded?*
- *Has the correct application form been used?*
- *Have all form sections been completed?*
- *Are the crowns of trees shown in metres?*

With the methods in this work we can categorise what types of files have been supplied but are not yet able to capture the context of which files should have been supplied in the first place, as these may change depending on the type of application. A small extension to the current work would be to check that all the files/objects expected in *any* application have been detected.

Verifying that all the sections of a form have been completed would likely require a combination of computer vision and text based approaches. Given a suitably annotated dataset with examples of complete and incomplete forms, a text-based classifier (similar to Section 3.3) or object detection model (similar to Section 4) could be trained to distinguish between the two cases.

Out of scope of the current work:

- *Does the description of work in the form match the drawings?*
- *Has the correct planning application fee been calculated?*
- *Are floor plans correct?*
- *Are block/site plans correct?*
- *Are all scales correct?*
- *Is True North correct?*

Verifying not only whether files/objects have been provided but rather whether they are correct in the context of an application is challenging from a modelling perspective and has not been considered within the time constraints of this work. For example, verifying whether a true north symbol is correct would require cross-checking the orientation of a map-like image in a drawing with an external map source.

5.2 Recommendations and Further Work

There are detailed comments and suggestions for all the approaches in the main body of the report. Here we summarise the key points and possible future research avenues.

5.2.1 Validate and fine-tune all the presented results

The work presented in this report are proof of concepts developed during a week-long hackathon-style event and therefore should be considered as preliminary. All results should be fully validated. In general we used algorithms and libraries with their default values and higher accuracies are likely to be achievable with fine-tuning.

5.2.2 Text-based approaches

For the purpose of training the document classification model we focus on text generated with OCR. Although OCR works for a wider range of documents, extracting text directly from the PDF is a simpler and faster process so verifying what can be done without OCR would be worthwhile. Our OCR approach may fail for rotated text and handwritten text, so more sophisticated methods may be explored.

We trained a simple “bag-of-words” model, using counts of words only. Alternative approaches may be able to retain more of the meaning and context of the content. Popular methods that could be applied here include topic analysis models [37] and word embeddings such as word2vec [38].

5.2.3 Image-based approaches

We trained a model capable of locating drawings and drawing captions in planning documents but did not have time to implement our proposed approach for linking drawings with captions (Section 4.3).

Due to the limited number of labels available for this dataset, it may be interesting to investigate unsupervised approaches (which don’t require labels). One example is image segmentation to cluster and separate different parts of a planning document. For possible future work using small details of plans, it may also be more efficient to perform an initial pre-processing step on a low resolution image to highlight areas of interest in the document, followed by a secondary analysis step on a high resolution image limited to those areas of interest.

5.2.4 Combine text- and image-based approaches

We treated text and image data separately but combining the two could be beneficial. For example, the object detection model can be used to identify a drawing and the location of its caption, but this could then be combined with a text-based classifier to categorise the type of drawing based on the words in its caption. We also considered the whole contents of a form as unstructured free

text. Object detection could be used to extract sections of the form separately, thereby retaining its structure.

5.2.5 Create labelled datasets

The lack of labelled data was a key limitation for this work, especially given the time constraints. The object detection model in Section 4 was trained using a dataset of just 30 manually labelled images, for example. This will also be a limiting factor for any future work. Approaches to generate more labelled data include:

- Active learning [39] can be used to iteratively label data, with the user (labeller) presented examples which the current model is unsure how to classify.
- Crowdsourcing, on platforms such as Zooniverse [40], could be used to recruit members of the public to annotate planning documents.
- Generating artificial data. A tool could be developed to populate blank form templates with known values, for example.

5.2.6 Data format

Anything that could be done to either a) reduce the reliance on PDFs in favour of structured (tabular) data, and/or b) standardise the layout of the PDFs, would be helpful. For example, form data could be stored in a database, which could then be easily queried to determine whether information was supplied for all the required fields. Alternatively, for drawings, stipulations such as requiring each file to contain a single drawing would simplify the process needed to analyse them. We acknowledge the complexity of planning applications makes standardisation difficult, but nevertheless emphasise it as an important consideration for the long term.

6 Team members

- **Adriaan Hilbers** is a PhD student in statistics applied to renewable energy at Imperial College London. Before his PhD, he studied mathematics and theoretical physics at Oxford and worked as a strategy consultant in Amsterdam. He was the facilitator for this group, organising workflows and compiling the report.
- **Alexandros Bertzouanis** works as a BIM Coordinator - Computational Specialist in Wilkinson Eyre. He is an Architect, a BIM expert and a coder integrating computational techniques into Architecture. He holds a master in Adaptive Architecture and Computation, UCL. He extracted and analysed the image metadata/statistics from the planning application PDFs.
- **Anna Hadjitofi** has a background in neuroscience and computer science, and has recently joined the Research Engineering group at The Alan Turing Institute. She was involved with implementing the object detection computer vision approach used to detect components of the drawing plans.
- **Antoine Choffrut** has held postdoctoral positions from 2009 until 2018 in Germany and the United Kingdom. His research was in mathematics, and more specifically in the analysis of partial differential equations. He has since turned to data science and is particularly interested in its application to information security.
- **Anthony Peake** is the CEO of Agile Datum and was the project sponsor and set the challenge for the Data Discovery Group hackathon. Anthony has over 35 years experience in the IT industry and in leading innovation teams for Apple, GE, BT and Oracle before starting his own AI and data science companies.
- **Carlos Mougan** has been involved in various kind of projects, from research in Deep Learning in the Spanish National Research Council, applied Data Science in the Barcelona Supercomputing Center to applied AI in the industry and finance. He also really enjoys attending Data Science challenges, and in the past years has enrolled in over 20+ datathons, achieving top places in some of them. He helped across the different technical problems, specifically in building the first multi-classification model.
- **Flora Roumpani** is a Research Associate at The Alan Turing Institute, a Visiting Lecturer in the Royal College of Arts and an architect. She holds a PhD from the Bartlett Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis (CASA) in UCL. She assisted with the image labelling, and image recognition tasks, and worked on the allocation of labels to drawings.
- **Jack Roberts** is a data scientist in the Research Engineering Group at The Alan Turing Institute. He was the principle investigator (PI) for this group, organising the preparatory work for the challenge, the Turing-Agile Datum relationship, and assisted with the technical work and admin related to the secure environment during the week, as well as editing the final report.

- **Piers Taylor** is the AI Solutions Architect at Agile Datum, and assisted the other participants in the challenge throughout the week. He has brought his knowledge in the planning domain, as well as his 30 years experience in the IT industry leading development projects including AI in Planning for the London Borough of Redbridge.

• **Zachary Price** is a Data scientist at Agile Datum, and assisted the other participants in the challenge throughout the week. He has recently joined Agile Datum after graduating in Computer Science in 2019 and brought his knowledge in the planning domain, as well as his skills with object detection and image recognition techniques.

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